

Minutes of the 61st Experimenters' Meeting The Cosener's House, Abingdon, 26th July 2018

(This document was finalised on 29th January 2019)

Present:

(CG)	Dr Catherine Gaffard ²	
(DAH)	Dr David Hooper ^{3,4,5}	Secretary
(EGN)	Dr Emily Norton ^{3,6}	
(GAP)	Dr Graham Parton ^{1,3,5}	
(GM)	Dr Graeme Marlton ⁷	
(GV)	Prof Geraint Vaughan ^{3,6}	Chair
(HMAR)	Dr Hugo Ricketts ^{3,6}	
(JP)	Dr Jeremy Price ²	
(LD)	Mr Les Dean ⁴	
(TG)	Mr Thomas Hargy ⁶	

Affiliation:

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²Met Office

³National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS)

⁴NERC MST Radar Facility

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Other abbreviations used in this document:

BLWP	Boundary-Layer Wind-Profiler
CFARR	Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research
EUCOS	EUMETNET Composite Observing System
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply
UTC	(Coordinated) Universal Time

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

GAP had spotted a few minor typographical errors in the minutes of the previous meeting and had already passed on the details to DAH. Moreover, he thought that the description, on page 8, of storm Fionn "developing via a non-Shapiro-Kaiser mechanism" was a bit inaccurate. He suggested that it would have been better to say that it did not follow the Shapiro-Kaiser model for cyclogenesis.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 47.2.1 DAH to modify the MST radar signal processing software, as soon as possible, to allow it to make use of updated Python programming libraries.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this action had become a high priority owing to a hard disk problem on computer "claudius", which processes MST radar data. The computer became unresponsive and stopped updating the latest data plots on Saturday 31st March 2018. LD rebooted it on the following day, which resulted in it become intermittently responsive. Although its performance returned to normal a few days later, DAH installed a replacement PC "germanicus" when he visited the radar site on 9th April. DAH had struggled to find and install all of the legacy python packages on which the processing software depends. He has decided that his time will be better spent on completing action item 47.2.1. This will also allow him to run the software on the jasmin system and to extend the back-processing of MST Radar data to the whole observation archive.

ACTION ITEM 47.3.2 DAH to recreate cloud base altitude files, starting from 2nd November 2010, with the time stamps corrected.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had made no direct progress on this action since the last meeting. Nevertheless, he has been helping Judith Jeffery to define netCDF files that are compliant with NCAS's data standards for a ceilometer operated by the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (CFARR). The same structure can then be used for data from the MSTRF's instrument. Previously, only cloud base data were made available and these were in NASA Ames format files. DAH added that he can already produce one-off files on request and that he had already done this for HMAR in connection with Storm Ophelia.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.1 DAH to increase the storage capacity of the Frongoch data logger so that communications failures do not lead to data loss.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this action was ongoing at that he would give more details in section 4a.

ACTION ITEM 51.4.2 DAH to make the Met Office's model-comparison statistics for the MST radar permanently available to users if the Met Office will allow this.

ONGOING

DAH reported that this is currently his lowest priority item and that no progress had been made since the previous meeting.

ACTION ITEM 58.1.1 DAH to consult with members of the data user community in order to establish the sort of instrument performance details that would be useful.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had heard from Chris Lee again, but that he had received no details relevant to this action item. GV pointed out that EGN was following up on Chris Lee's work, so this could be important. He suggested maybe including the transmitter status details within the products files.

ACTION ITEM 59.3.1 DAH to arrange for the clearance of willow saplings from the MST radar's antenna array as soon as possible.

ONGOING

DAH will report on this in section 3d.

ACTION ITEM 60.2.1 DAH to extend the availability of the v4 Cardinal files back to the earliest date for which v3 Cartesian files are available.

ONGOING

DAH reported that he had not yet done this, but since all of the necessary software is in place, it can easily be undertaken.

3. Facility Report - DAH

Full details of facility and instrument performance issues can be found at http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/cgi-bin/mstlog_public/mst_event_search.py.

3a) Data Management

GAP began this section by reporting on recent developments at CEDA. The catalogue pages have been given a new appearance and some bugs have been sorted out. In the case of dataset pages covering netCDF files, the “Variables” tab now gives a list of variables sorted by their long names. This revealed that the long name for the variable `final_velocity_bin_number` in version 3 MST radar radial files inadvertently starts with a “(“. Clicking on the long name provides details of their other attributes. A full scan of the 160 million files in the archive has confirmed that most of them are covered by the catalogue. Those files that are not are typically plots.

EGN asked why it was not possible to find quick-look plots through the catalogue pages. She thought that these were one of the most useful things associated with a dataset and that they should be the first thing that a user finds. GAP clarified that CEDA deliberately avoided indexing plots. Nevertheless, links to the plots can be found under the “Details/Docs” tab of associated dataset pages. Look under the “Related Documents” section. EGN took a look at one of the revised pages during the meeting and pronounced them to be an improvement. GV added that this tab could be better labelled.

GAP then gave an update on how the MSTRF dataset has been accessed through CEDA over the past 12 months. The total number of users was 205, although the vast majority of these (186) only accessed quick-look plots. Sixty per cent of users are from the UK. The Vaisala WXT510 data have been popular, as have been the version 3 and version 4 MST radar data files.

DAH reported that he had made a slight improvement to the way in which he deals with data files as they pass through his “quarantine” system. Since April 2017 he has been examining the associated quick-look plots before he decides whether or not the files contain any bad data. For netCDF files that are deemed to be free of problems, the “*history*” global attribute is automatically updated with an entry stating, “*Data passed visual quality control check and file delivered to CEDA for ingestion into archives.*”. Since June 2018 the process has been extended so that the reason for a file being withheld is also recorded within its “*history*”. Previously these details were only recorded externally by the instrument performance weblog. This means that if anyone requests access to a withheld file, it will be clear that the file contains suspect data.

GV pointed out that people will not ask for access to withheld files if they do not know that they exist. He also thought it unlikely that people would read the global attributes on a routine basis. He noted that the files in question only contained suspect data within limited time-altitude regions and so should not be withheld on this basis. He asked DAH and GAP to devise a mechanism for making such files available whilst clearly indicating their suspect status.

ACTION ITEM 61.3.1 DAH and GAP to implement a mechanism for releasing files containing small amounts of suspect data to the CEDA archives and of labelling them in such a way that their suspect status is obvious.

NEW

3b) Electricity - DAH

During the past 6 months, the Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units experienced short-lived (i.e. no more than 1 s) input power problems on 5 days. These all occurred during March 2018.

There appears to have been a prolonged loss of input power between 04:37 and 05:39 UTC on Saturday 12th May 2018. This led to the UPS units becoming discharged. DAH had initially assumed that the failure of the latest data quick-look plots to be updated was the result of an ongoing internet problem - see next section. He had to remotely reboot both the radar control and beam steering computers (julius and tiberius) before he could restart the MST Radar at 08:13 UTC. He restarted the Vaisala WXT520 data acquisition at 10:54 UTC. The computer (gaius) that acquires the Vaisala LD40 did not restart automatically when the input power was restored. However, since LD had to be on site later that morning to wait for an Openreach engineer - see next section - has was able to restart it shortly afterwards.

3c) Telecommunications

The internet connection to the site was lost at around 03:15 UTC on Wednesday 9th May 2018. When DAH reported this to the internet service provider later that morning, they thought that it might be a result of a "regrade" being carried out on the Capel Bangor telephone exchange. However, the problem persisted after this work was completed. The MSTRF's router was switched to the University of Manchester line on Friday 11th in order to clear some of the backlog of file transfers. An Openreach engineer visited the site on the afternoon of Saturday 12th and confirmed that the problem had been at the exchange. DAH was due to be out of the office for the following 2 weeks - attending the NCAS atmospheric measurement course on the Isle of Arran - and so would have had difficulties in attending to the problem if it had persisted.

3d) Miscellaneous

DAH reported that MSTRF had officially merged with the Chilbolton Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (CFARR) on 1st April 2018. This will not affect how users interact with or gain support from the two nodes of the new NERC Facility for Atmospheric Radar Research (NFARR). The merger was mandated by NERC as a condition for the renewal of funding, with the understanding that NFARR will merge with the Atmospheric Measurement Facility (AMF) in April 2020.

A Health and Safety inspection of the MST Radar site was carried out by a member of RAL staff on 13th June 2018. The site was given an overall score of 4, indicating that only minor improvements were needed. The three most significant issues were as follows: Portable Appliance Testing is out of date, the growth of willow saplings within the antenna array is considered a Health and Safety Risk, and the fire extinguisher in the wooden shed has not been checked for a number of years.

DAH reported that he is still trying to set up a contract for the willow sapling clearance through STFC. However, progress has been very slow. GV emphasised the fact that this job was extremely important and that DAH should makes this his highest priority.

4. NERC Instrument Report - DAH

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

There have been no problems with these sensors during the past 6 months. DAH had initially been surprised that the tipping bucket raingauge detected an accumulation of 1.8 mm of rain during the period 17:30 - 18:50 UTC on 23rd July 2018 when the Vaisala WXT520 detected nothing. Precipitation is often

revealed by vertical features in plots of LD40 laser ceilometer backscatter power. However, in this case the cloud base was too low to allow such a signature to be discernible. There was no sign of convection in the MST radar observations at this time, although stratocumulus might be undetected if the cloud top doesn't rise significantly above the lowest radar range gate. Moreover, not all rain is associated with convective processes. Images from Sky-Camera-2 revealed that the valley was shrouded in ground level cloud. This suggests that the rain was falling too slowly to be detected by the WXT520's piezo-electric sensor.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors

DAH had reported at the last meeting that the Campbell Scientific logger was intermittently recording values of 0.0 for both wind speed and direction, sometimes for extended periods. The logger started to record realistic-looking values during the 2nd half of 21st February 2018 and has been doing so ever since. Nevertheless, a new logger (a Campbell Scientific CR1000X) has been purchased and will replace the existing one in the near future. The plan is to switch to using a 3G data connection rather than relying on a dial-up modem via one of Aberystwyth University's land lines. Since the MSTRF does not pay the bills for this line, it has no authority to initiate tests if a fault occurs.

DAH has looked into the details of how both the Campbell Scientific and Vaisala WXT510/WXT520 units derive their 1 minute interval winds. This was initiated by GAP asking him to create a quality statement for the WXT510 dataset. However, this information is also necessary in order to ensure that the new Campbell Scientific logger use an identical sampling strategy to the existing one. The Campbell Scientific logger begins by sampling the direction and speed (from the wind vane and anemometer, respectively) at 1 s intervals. The mean speed for each minute is defined as the mean of all 60 raw values over the minute. Gust speeds are derived by applying a 3 s running mean to the 1 s interval raw values. The minimum and maximum gust speed values for each minute are recorded. Finally the 1 s direction values are converted into unit vectors, which are averaged over the minute in order to give the mean direction.

The Vaisala WXT510/WXT520 instruments use sonic anemometers and so speed and direction are derived from the same set of underlying measurements. The winds are sampled 4 times a second over 3 s, followed by a gap of 57 s. Since this sampling strategy captures less of the wind's variation over 1 minute compared to the strategy used by the Campbell Scientific logger, the ratio of the maximum gust speed to the mean speed is significantly smaller. DAH recommended a World Meteorological Organisation technical report (number 1555) by Harper et al. (2010) for further reading on this subject - https://www.wmo.int/pages/prog/www/tcp/documents/WMO_TD_1555_en.pdf. Although it is concerned with tropical cyclones, it covers all of the concepts relevant to the above.

4c) Vaisala WXT510/WXT520 surface met and wind sensors

DAH presented another piece of analysis that he had undertaken for the purpose of the WXT510 quality statement. He has long known that the wind direction measured by the WXT510 is tightly constrained by the approximately ENE-WSW alignment of the valley in which it is located - scroll to the bottom of page <http://mst.nerc.ac.uk/wxt510.html>. By contrast, the the Campbell Scientific sensors at Frongoch are located at the top of a hill and the measured directions are assumed to be representative of the broader-scale flow. DAH has created a wind rose showing the relative frequencies of wind directions measured at both Capel Dewi and Frongoch. At present the plot only covers the period 22nd December 2007 - 21st December 2008 and uses unsmoothed 1 minute interval winds. However, it will be easy to extend this to include data from the following 6 years during which the WXT510 was in operation. Moreover, DAH has discovered that the Ordnance Survey have made made a number of datasets open access - <https://www.ordnancesurvey.co.uk/opendatadownload/products.html>. These include "OS Terrain 50" which covers mainland Britain at horizontal intervals of 50 m. DAH showed a 20 km by 20 km plot covering both Frongoch and Capel Dewi. It shows the orientation of the Capel Dewi valley very clearly. Ordnance Survey appear to have discontinued their earlier "Get-

A-Map” service, which allowed a small number of map sections to be used on websites. DAH aims to make his OS Terrain 50 data reading routines openly-available.

DAH has discovered that there are occasional periods when the wind speed recorded by the WXT510 increases to values significantly in excess of those recorded simultaneously at Frongoch. Moreover, the WXT510 wind direction changes rapidly during such periods and is frequently other than the predominant ENE and WSW. This means that the magnitude of the 15 minute running mean of the wind vector can drop close to zero. A running mean of wind speed rather than wind vector is more representative under such circumstances. DAH speculated that these features might be indicative of rotor activity. He showed one example from 22nd January 2008 when the Frongoch measurements showed an approximately southerly direction, i.e. quasi-perpendicular to the orientation of the valley. The peak WXT510 wind speed was approximately 30 m s^{-1} compared with under 10 m s^{-1} for Frongoch.

JP wasn't sure if a rotor was responsible, but thought that the measurements showed some sort of turbulence feature. He recommended that DAH add concentric circles to his wind rose so that the percentages of time spent within each direction range were more immediately obvious. He suggested that Andrew Ross at the University of Leeds might be interested in this valley flow dataset. He suggested that it would be useful to record 1 s interval wind samples, since these provide more detail.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

There have been no issues relating to this instrument over the past 6 months. GM expressed an interest in the observations since stratocumulus clouds play a role in atmospheric electricity. He would be interested to install electric field mills in the vicinity but wasn't sure where would be the most appropriate location.

4e) Sky Cameras

The release of images from Sky-Camera-2 and from the NLC camera is awaiting DAH's finalisation of the metadata to be embedded within the image files. Barbara Brooks wants to use these examples as templates for other scientific images captured as part of NCAS activities.

4f) Noctilucent Cloud (NLC) Camera

The computer (twilight) used to capture images from the NLC Camera developed problems at the beginning of the 2018 season. This led to gaps in the record, with no images captured at all on some nights. Consequently a new computer was installed on 15th June. After a slow start to the season, NLCs were seen on 5 nights out of 6 during the period between 22nd and 27th June. Robust mesospheric echoes were also seen frequently by the MST radar at around this time. The season became much quieter, in terms of both NLCs and radar echoes, during the course of July. JP pointed out that the Met Office have a space weather group, who might be interested in these observations.

4g) MST Radar

DAH began by presenting model-comparison statistics for the past six months, which had been prepared by Caroline Bulpitt of the Met Office. EUCOS statistics show that data availability has been fairly constant, although there were a couple of days with very low values in late December 2017. The reason for these is not clear. The root mean square wind mean vector differences were mostly below the 5.0 m s^{-1} target maximum. Much larger values on 20th October 2017 correspond to the beam steering unit problems following a power cut - see section 3b. Comparisons against the Met Office's UKV model also show good data quality over the past six months.

DAH then gave a general instrument performance report. Data files for a number of days have not been released to the CEDA archives owing to features that have not been blanked by the automatic quality control algorithms. "Old school interference" affecting a large number of range gates was seen on 4th February 2018 and, to a lesser extent, on 4th March. This led to large time-altitude gaps in coverage.

Data between 01:00 and 03:00 UTC on 25th March 2018 was affected by a known bug that is only apparent when the clocks change between Greenwich Mean Time (GMT) and British Summer Time (BST). Wind speeds that are significantly faster than those seen at adjacent times and altitudes were seen on 3rd, 12th, and 19th June 2018. GV re-emphasised the need to allow files that contained suspect data within small time-altitude regions into the CEDA archives. He suggested, in particular, that the although the data for 4th February 2018 were very gappy, they did not appear to be contaminated with suspect data. Consequently they should be released.

There have been only 2 times when transmitter B has been out of action and 3 times for transmitter C. Transmitters A and E were both powered down on 16th March 2018, when Aberystwyth University students were conducting their surveying exercise.

5. Guest Instrument Report

EGN reported that the BLWP had experienced various problems since it returned from a deployment in Portugal during the spring of 2017. One of these problems was caused by water getting into the power splitter. The instrument has been reliable since October 2017. It is likely to remain at Capel Dewi for the foreseeable future.

Philipp Currier, the main person responsible for BLWPs at the manufacturer Degreane, will be retiring on 1st August 2018. He will be missed. He hopes to continue working on a few interesting issues, such as making processed data available in netCDF files. Although these won't be compliant with the NCAS data standards, they will be much easier to access than the existing files, which use a bespoke binary format that has changed slightly over time.

Data from the BLWP have not been accepted by the Met Office for some time. At one point there was a confusion caused by the BLWP's name being mapped onto the Aberystwyth MST radar. Another problem was caused by the BLWP trying to connect to the Met Office up to 1 million times per day.

HMAR reported that he had spent the final week of March 2018 at the MST radar site. His principal task was to get a Raman channel working on the Elight lidar. It is working after a fashion, although there are some outstanding issues, which may be caused by alignment problems. Dave Wareing has built an alignment tool. TG will be analysing water vapour lidar data from the NAWDEX campaign period.

GV reported that a paper looking on biofluorescent aerosol emissions, based on guest instrument measurements at the MST radar site, is currently under review - <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-2018-513>.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Intercomparison between UHF and VHF winds - EGN

The BLWP has been in operation at the MST radar site since October 2017. The primary aim is to follow up on a comparison of the wind profiles measured by the two radars. This follows on work initiated by Chris Lee in 2014, which showed that there was generally good agreement where the signal-to-noise ratio was high. The standard deviation of a comparison between BLWP and tower data was 2.3 m s^{-1} . A digital inclinometer has been used to ensure that the vertical BLWP antenna panel is accurately aligned. This was one of the suspected sources of error from the earlier work. Horizontal winds from both the BLWP and MST radar represent 30 minute averages. High-mode BLWP data were chosen since the 275 m range resolution is comparable to the 300 m resolution used by the MST radar. Under precipitation conditions the vertical velocity measured by the BLWP represents the fall speed of hydrometeors whereas that measured by the MST represent represents the air speed. Consequently precipitation and non-precipitation conditions have been analysed separately. The horizontal winds generally agree well, although there is some evidence of ground clutter affecting the BLWP measurements. The BLWP vertical velocities show a negative bias relative to the MST measurements (GV pointed out that the previous

work had shown a positive bias).

The BLWP will remain at Capel Dewi for the foreseeable future. EGN will try reprocessing the BLWP data with different settings in the Degreane software. Issues with ground clutter still need to be resolved. The previous work was carried out under conditions of predominantly westerly winds. The present deployment will capture a wider range of conditions.

6b) Wind-profiler backscatter estimation of refractive index gradient - CG

This work is motivated by the fact that the vertical gradient of refractive index depends on the vertical profiles of temperature and humidity. If it could be retrieved from BLWP signal power, the high temporal and vertical resolutions of the observations would make them ideally suited for assimilation into a numerical weather prediction scheme. One of the problems is that there are potentially 3 different backscatter mechanisms. It is currently assumed that Bragg scatter from refractive index irregularities is the primary mechanism. This is tested using 2 years' of Camborne BLWP observations combined with co-located radiosonde and model data.

The backscatter model is built on the previous work of Tatarski (1961), Gossard (1982, 1988), and White (1999). It takes backscatter power, vertical wind shear, and spectral width into consideration. CG has used the Jacoby-Koaly et al. (2002) formula for beam broadening spectral width and has validated this against Chen (2011). It shows a small, asymmetric dependence on azimuth angle. The shear correction turns out to be significant and must be applied individually for each beam - not for the combination of data from opposing off-vertical beams. The scatter plot of observed spectral width against wind speed shows that the expected beam broadening contribution is a good indicator of the smallest observed value. Moreover, the corrected values do not show a dependence on wind speed, which suggests that the correction is appropriate.

The relationship between BLWP backscatter power and expected values based on model or radiosonde data is quite variable. It was typically best for clear sky/fair weather conditions when there was a temperature inversion present. Although the profiles can be well matched qualitatively, if there is a small altitude offset between the observed and predicted patterns, the quantitative differences can be large. Consequently, an alternative approach is to shift the profile vertically so that the maxima and minima are aligned. The fit between model and radiosonde values is better than that between BLWP power and the others. However, CG noted that the model assimilates data from the radiosondes. Using different selection procedures, such as ignoring cloudy conditions, did not improve the fit between BLWP and model/radiosonde values.

CG wondered, amongst other things, if the fit might have been better if vertical beam observations were available since wind shear could be ignored. GV suggested that patchy and/or fossil turbulence may need to be taken into account. DAH pointed out that the formulae linking backscatter power to refractive index gradient implicitly required active turbulence. CG pointed out that the use of spectral width in the retrieval did not obviously improve the results.

6c) A fresh look at the correction of MST radar spectral widths in order to retrieve turbulence information - DAH

This work, like that presented by CG, assumes that MST radar return signals are dominated by backscatter from refractive index irregularities. If the latter are generated by turbulent mixing that fills the depth of a radar observation volume, the backscatter is expected to be isotropic. However, since it is not known for how long isotropy persists after mixing ceases, low aspect sensitivity (i.e. a near-zero variation in radar return power as a function of beam pointing zenith angle) is a necessary but insufficient condition to indicate active turbulence. The spectral width must be considered in addition. Some authors - such as Nastrom (1997) and Dehghan and Hocking (2011) - have proposed procedures for extracting the turbulent broadening width from the observed values that involve multiple terms. However, it's not clear that

these add anything useful after the basic beam broadening term (which depends only on wind speed and beam width) is taken into consideration.

In order to evaluate the simple correction procedure, DAH has plotted profiles of uncorrected vertical beam spectral width from consecutive observation cycles over 1 hour. On the same plot he has shown a profile of the expected beam broadening contribution (based on the mean wind speed over the same period) and of the mean uncorrected vertical beam spectral width. Using data from one of GM's turbulence campaign periods, a number of issues are immediately apparent. Firstly, it is clear that the variations in time of the uncorrected values are significantly larger than the difference between the mean value and the expected beam broadening value. This indicates that single cycle estimates of corrected spectral width are of limited value. Secondly, the uncorrected values are often smaller than the expected beam broadening value. Since a negative corrected value has no meaning, this suggests that the uncorrected values should be averaged in time before being corrected - not corrected on a cycle by cycle basis before being averaged. The former approach is currently used for the v3 and v4 processing schemes. The latter approach is consistent with a point made by Dehghan and Hocking (2011), which DAH had initially thought was of limited significance. Finally, the averaged uncorrected values are sometimes significantly less than the predicted beam broadening values. These appear to be associated with regions of large aspect sensitivity. Interestingly, the means of the uncorrected spectral widths observed at 6° off-vertical are typically closer to the predicted beam broadening values under such circumstances. Although more work is needed to follow up on these results, they suggest the treatment of spectral width data could be significantly improved.

7. Any Other Business

GV initiated a discussion of whether it would be useful to install additional instruments for observing the boundary layer at Capel Dewi. There are already people within NCAS who are interested in valley flows. JP pointed out that the Capel Dewi valley is quite small and so it is not clear whether detailed studies of it would have broader scientific applicability. The LANFEX campaign had been conducted in much deeper valleys in east Wales, with a particular emphasis on studying fog formation. He thought that it would only be worthwhile to install a 20 m tower at Capel Dewi if research-grade equipment were installed on it. For example, the Met Office log the raw data from their sonic anemometers directly to a computer. He was not sure if a data logger would be able to cope with the high data rate. Even with a 10 m flux tower, it would be necessary to install 2 short wave and 2 long wave radiometers. The LANFEX campaign had revealed the need for additional measurements to supplement the primary ones, but only after the event. The Met Office had opted to focus on a distributed network of sensors rather than on a single super site. It's not clear where else in the Capel Dewi valley additional sensors could be located, both from an access and a (power and internet) infrastructure point of view. GV pointed out that Bogdan Antonescu had been keen to place sensors around the valley. Although there is not sufficient staff time available to maintain such a network on a full time basis, it might be possible for a limited campaign period.

The data for the next meeting was provisionally set for late January 2019.